

Hospital Financial Performance and Quality of Care: Evidence from Portugal

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Following the economic crisis, Portuguese hospitals experienced severe budget cuts and had to implement cost-containment strategies. It is ambiguous whether such measures led to changes in quality of services they provided. This paper aims at investigating the relationship between hospital financial performance and quality of hospital care using panel data on Portuguese public hospitals for the period of 2007-2017. Moreover, the economic literature on the association between hospital finances and quality of care is very scarce, hence this study aims at filling the existing void in the European health setting.

Methodology: We construct a set of financial indicators reflecting profitability and indebtedness of hospitals using information from hospital monthly financial reports. We utilize hospital-level diagnosis-related group (DRG) data to construct quality of care measures, including overall and disease-specific mortality rates and readmissions, while distinguishing between typically high and low mortality DRGs. We then combine these data with local municipality level variables reflecting market characteristics and hospital-level variables accounting for the case-mix of patients to develop a model of potential determinants of hospital care quality. Additionally, we construct patient safety indicators as hospital acquired infections obtained from procedure codes in the DRG data and use them as dependent variables thereby seeking to answer whether hospital financial conditions may compromise patient safety. We adopt the partial adjustment mechanism accounting for lags in the response of quality to changing financial conditions and address potential endogeneity by employing two estimation methods: system GMM approach and fixed effects estimation. Moreover, we perform the analysis using different time setting to pinpoint how fast the response occurs.

Results: Preliminary results show that there is a positive relationship between hospital's financial condition and quality of services it provides. However, the significance and magnitude of the impact depend on specific financial and quality indicators used, which suggests that some measures may not be sensitive enough to reflect the impact. Moreover, the partial adjustment mechanism turned out to be justified indicating that quality of care takes time to respond to financial changes and therefore needs to be accounted for when investigating this relationship. Furthermore, certain hospital and patient characteristics seem to have a consistent pattern of effect on the quality of hospital care. Meanwhile, no significant impact of hospital finances on patient safety has been identified.

Discussion: The findings suggest that financial hardship experienced by public hospitals imposes limits on hospital's ability to invest in quality improving measures but does not seem to compromise patient safety. Nevertheless, further investigation is needed to understand exact mechanisms through which the impact occurs, as well as alternative quality of care and patient safety indicators should be used for sensitivity checks. Noteworthy, this is the first research that utilizes continuous financial data rather than a policy change or event occurrence and addresses the relationship between hospital finances and quality of their services in a European setting. It has direct implications for policy and practice, especially given the recent change of Portuguese law allowing patients to choose hospital thereby enhancing quality competition among hospitals.